

Maxwell's Equations for a Photon and Quantum Mechanics

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In (1), it is argued that Maxwell's equations for E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) for a photon (no charges or current) are quantum mechanical equations akin to Dirac's equation. In fact, a vector wavefunction is set to $E+iB$ (E and B being vectors). In (1), the first step is to take the energy conservation equation for a photon, $E_0=p$ or $E_0= \sqrt{pp}$ ($c=1$) and to find operators such that $E_0W = \sqrt{pp}W$ where W is a vector wavefunction representing spin 1. It is argued that $E_0 \rightarrow i\partial/\partial t$ and \sqrt{pp} is replaced with $-i \text{grad} \times$ (where \times is the curl). As a second step, it is shown that W^*W leads to the energy density $.5(EE+BB)$.

In this note, we wish to take a different approach, but obtain the same result. In (2), we argued that for a quantum free particle, $\exp(ipx)$ represents a quantity whose modulus is 1 everywhere, but shows dynamics. In other words, $P(x)=\text{constant}$ and $P(p/x)=\exp(ipx)$. The form $\exp(ipx)$ is chosen to satisfy $-i\partial/\partial x P(p/x) = p P(p/x)$ i.e. we argue that the change in conditional probability is proportional to momentum. Similarly, $\exp(-iEot)$ is used to describe energy. These ideas are combined with a conservation of energy equation to obtain the free particle Schrodinger equation. A similar approach may be used for the free particle Klein-Gordon equation. Alternatively (3), one may consider a free particle Lagrangian $m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ or $.5mvv$ for the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases. Using $\exp(i \text{Action})$ with $\text{Action}= L T$ for a free particle leads to $i\partial/\partial t \exp(i \text{Action})= E_0 \exp(i \text{Action})$ and $-i\partial/\partial x \exp(i \text{Action}) = p \exp(i \text{Action})$. This also may be used to convert a conservation of energy equation into a quantum mechanical differential equation.

We argue in this note that these statistical (fluctuation) arguments should also apply to a photon. Thus, we start with $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ as a conditional type of probability for a photon. In electromagnetism, however, there is energy density $=.5(EE +BB)$ where E and B are electric and magnetic fields. This is equivalent to $.5(E+iB)(E-iB)$ which has the form of $.5 W^* W$. Thus, we consider $E+iB$ as a conditional energy probability quantity which should be proportional to $\exp(ipx-iEot)$ E and B should both satisfy a wave equation, i.e. the Klein-Gordon equation, in order to obtain such a result because $E_0=p$. If one wishes to couple E and B , then $dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B$ and $dB/dt = -\text{grad}E$ lead to the wave equation, but allow one to write a Dirac type equation (nomenclature from (1)) i.e. $i\partial/\partial t W = \text{grad} \times W$ where $W=E+iB$ the vector wavefunction.

If Maxwell's equations are really quantum mechanical equations as argued in (1), then these were derived in a macroscopic environment and in fact there are electromagnetic waves (radio waves) with macroscopic wavelengths.

Maxwell's Equations for a Photon and a Quantum Wave Equation (Following (1))

In (1), it is argued that Maxwell's equations for a photon are really quantum mechanical equations similar to the Dirac equation. The authors start with Einstein's momentum energy

equation: $E_0 E_0 = p p + m_0 m_0$, set $m_0=0$ and write $E_0 = \sqrt{p p}$. They then wish to have E_0 and $\sqrt{p p}$ represented by operators acting on W , a vector wavefunction with three components because a photon has spin 1. Specifically, they argue that:

$A A W = p p W$ where A is an operator leads to $A = i p \times$ where W is taken to be a transverse object i.e. $\text{grad} \cdot W = 0$. E_0 becomes $i d/dt$.

Thus $E_0 W(p, E_0) = p \times W(p, E_0)$ or $d/dt W(r, t) = \text{grad} \times W(r, t)$ ((1))

Next, they consider a normalization of $W^* W$ and conclude that this quantity is equivalent to $.5(E E + B B)$, the electromagnetic energy density.

Using $W = E + i B$ in ((1)) leads to Maxwell's equations for a photon:

$d/dt B = -\text{grad} \times E$ and $d/dt E = \text{grad} \times B$ ((2))

Full details of this approach are given in (1).

Statistical Approach and Conditional Probability

In this note, we begin with a statistical approach which applies to a particle with mass m_0 governed by $E E = p p + m_0 m_0$. The photon satisfies this equation with $m_0=0$ and so we argue similar ideas should hold. For a free particle, we argue that statistically it may be at any x with equal probability i.e. $P(x) = \text{constant}$, but this is an average value. We argue there are dynamics in the picture and that density is created by motion. Thus, we consider a conditional probability $\exp(i p x)$ such that its modulus is 1 satisfying $P(x) = \text{constant}$. There is nevertheless fluctuating or oscillating behaviour occurring. We argue that $-i d/dx P(p/x) = p P(p/x)$ i.e. p governs the rate of change of the conditional probability.

A second way to see these ideas is to consider $\exp(i \text{Action})$ (introduced by P. Dirac). For a free particle $\text{Action} = L T$ with $L = m_0 \sqrt{1 - v v}$ and $L = .5 m_0 v v$ for relativistic and nonrelativistic cases. Setting $v = X/T$ and allowing X and T to fluctuate independently (so $v = X/T = \text{constant}$ is only an average result) leads to: $i d/dt \exp(i \text{Action}) = E_0 \exp(i \text{Action})$ and $-i d/dx \exp(i \text{Action}) = p \exp(i \text{Action})$. One may thus use these results in a conservation of energy equation, converting it into a differential equation i.e. the Klein-Gordon or the Schrodinger equation. A solution is $\exp(-i E_0 t + i p x)$.

We argue that a photon should behave in a similar manner (as it satisfies the Klein-Gordon equation with $m_0=0$). Thus, there should be an $\exp(i p x - i E_0 t)$ term for a photon. What is $P(x)$ for a photon? For a particle $W(x) = \exp(i p x - i E_0 t)$ and $P(x) = W^* W$, but in electromagnetism there is an energy density:

Energy density = $.5(E E + B B) = .5 (E + i B)(E - i B)$ where E and B are electric and magnetic fields. ((2))

We argue that this is $P(x,t)$. So $E+iB$ is associated with the particle W or $\exp(ipx-iEot)$. Thus, we expect that for a photon:

$$E+iB = \exp(ipx-iEt) [Ea+iao] \text{ where } Ea \text{ and } Ba \text{ are vectors} \quad ((3))$$

If this is the case, one needs equations for E and B . A wave equation (i.e. the Klein-Gordon equation with $m_0=0$) works, but one may also have two linear equations:

$$dB/dt = -\text{grad} \times E \text{ and } dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B \text{ or } d/dt (E+iB) = \text{grad} \times (E+iB) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) has the benefit that it couples E and B whereas the Klein-Gordon approach treats E and B separately. ((4)) represent Maxwell's equations for a photon.

Thus, as argued in (1) Maxwell's equations for a photon appear to be quantum mechanical equations similar in nature to Dirac's solution. Dirac's solution for an electron satisfies a linear equation in d/dt and d/dx , but also satisfies the Klein-Gordon equation for a free particle. The photon scenario is very similar.

The approach presented here depends on $\exp(ipx-iEot)$ as a starting point for either a particle or photon.

Macroscopic Features of Quantum Mechanics

The electric and magnetic results, made by various people, which Maxwell wrote as equations of electromagnetism were based on macroscopic experiments. If one sets charged particles and currents to zero in these macroscopic equations, it is argued one obtains a quantum mechanical equation for the photon. Thus, quantum mechanics can exist on a macroscopic level it seems. Furthermore, there are electromagnetic waves (radio waves) with macroscopic wavelengths. According to (1), quantum mechanics was already being described by Maxwell when he considered electric and magnetic field equations for the photon.

Conclusion

The authors of (1) argue that the Maxwell equations in E and B (electric and magnetic fields) describing a photon are really quantum mechanical and similar to Dirac's equation. They begin with the idea of a vector wavefunction W and conservation of energy from Einstein's energy momentum relationship $E_0 = \sqrt{pp}$ and seek an operator A such that $AA W = pp W$. They conclude: $A = p \times$ is such an operator and propose: $id/dt W = -\text{grad} \times W$. They then consider normalization and find that $W^*W = EE+BB$ so $W = E+iB$ and $id/dt W = -\text{grad} \times W$, a quantum mechanical equation yields Maxwell's equations in E and B for a photon.

In this note, we argue that both a relativistic particle and photon satisfy $E_0E_0 = pp + m_0m_0$, but for the photon $m_0=0$. We argue that one expects a form $\exp(ipx-iEot)$ for both a particle and a photon based on statistical reasons. $\exp(ipx-iEot)$ is related to conditional probability which is linked to $P(x) = \text{constant}$ for a particle). For a photon, one has energy density instead given by $.5(EE+BB)$, thus $E+iB$ seems to be the form of conditional probability and it should be

proportional to $\exp(ipx-iEot)$. This suggests that E and B may both be solutions of a wave equation i.e. the Klein-Gordon equation. They may also be interlinked yielding the solution $-dB/dt = \text{grad} \times E$ and $dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B$. Thus, instead of looking directly for an operator equation acting on a vector wavefunction, we consider $\exp(ipx-iEot)$ as arising in a statistical manner for both a photon or particle and then consider the relationship to density or energy density. Finally, an equation is obtained to yield the $\exp(ipx-iEot)$ form.

References

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